

Table S2. Main elasmobranch bycatch species reported by fishing method and vessel class (IATTC categories) in the Colombian Pacific Ocean.

Main elasmobranch bycatch species	Years with bycatch	Fishing method	Vessel class (years reported)
Sharks			
<i>Alopias pelagicus</i> ; <i>A. superciliosus</i>	2003 2010, 2011	DEL, NoAs, NAT, FAD	3, 4 (2010, 2011) 5, 6 (2003-2009; 2013-2019)
<i>Carcharhinus cerdale</i>	2009, 2010, 2011	FAD, DEL, NoAs, NAT	3, 4, 6
<i>Carcharhinus faciformis</i>	2003 to 2019 except 2016	FAD, DEL, NAT, NoAs DEL (2016)	All vessel classes
<i>Carcharhinus leucas</i>	Only in 2007 and 2010	NAT, NoAs	All vessel classes
<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>	2006, 2007, 2010, 2011, 2014	FAD, DEL, NoAs	All vessel classes
<i>Carcharhinus obscurus</i>	2009, 2010, 2011	FAD, DEL, NoAs, NAT	3, 4, 6
<i>S. lewini</i>	All years except, 2003, 2008, 2012, 2014, 2017	FAD, DEL, NoAs, NAT	All vessel classes
<i>S. zygaena</i>	2006, 2010, 2014, 2018, 2019.	FAD, DEL, NoAs, NAT	All vessel classes
Mantas and Rays			
<i>Mobula thurstoni</i> , <i>M. tarapacana</i> , <i>M. munkiana</i>	2004, 2009, 2010, 2017	FAD, NoAs	All vessel classes
<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i>	2017	DEL	5, 6